

Design and modeling of a MEMS-based tunable optical nanoantenna

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Abstract: A MEMS-based tunable optical nanoantenna is described. The capability of the nanometer resolution and repeatability offered by the MEMS actuators paves the way for the tunable optical antennas, which is confirmed by both modeling and experimental measurements. The MEMS-based tunable antenna offers many advantages in terms of cost-effective fabrication, dynamic optical intensity enhancement, dynamic wavelength shifting and performance optimization, etc. The optical performance of the tunable antenna has been investigated using rigorous finite difference and time domain (FDTD) method. It reveals that peak wavelengths and local field enhancements are largely affected by the size and shape of the bowtie antenna. The optical field can be drastically enhanced by reducing the gap size less than 30 nm which can easily be achieved by the MEMS system.

1. Introduction

In order to analyze their properties in real-time using non-invasive optical technique with high resolution imaging and spectroscopy, the biomolecular nanostructures and the nanoscale materials need to be selectively illuminated, enabling spatial resolution beyond the diffraction limit. In this regard, the main promising tool is the near-field scanning optical microscopy (NSOM) [1, 2]. However, its optical transmission efficiency is very small, typically only about 1% for aperture NSOM. Some research using specific noble metal nanostructures has been performed to improve the transmission efficiency [3-6]. One approach is to utilize the optical bowtie antenna [3], a concept borrowed from microwave communication engineering. The optical antenna technique is also very useful for the improvement of the performance of the apertureless NSOM as well. The giant and highly localized enhancement of the optical field in the proximity of the sharp tip of the apertureless NSOM enables nanoscale resolution for both imaging and spectroscopy, such as the tip-enhanced Raman spectroscopy [7]. Furthermore, the optical antenna technique might further help improve many different other applications utilized by plasmonics and NSOM techniques, such as nanolithography [8], ultra-high density data storage [9], drug discovery [10] and nanoscale optical circuits [11], etc. However, due to the nanoscale gap between the two triangular structures, the bowtie antenna usually has to be fabricated using expensive advanced nanofabrication technology such as electron-beam lithography [4-6], a major drawback to its wide and inexpensive applications. Furthermore, for all of the reported optical bowtie antennas, they are not tunable with a fixed gap between the two triangular structures. Once fabricated, they are only suitable for the signal enhancement for certain specific wavelengths [6]. Therefore, different antennas have to be designed and fabricated for the enhancement for different wavelengths for the optimal conditions. Recently a MEMS-based bowtie antenna with integrated electrostatic actuators has been reported [12]. This work did NOT explore the tunable properties of the antenna. In addition, the operation voltage is as high as 70V.

In this paper, a MEMS-based tunable optical antenna is reported for the *first* time. First, using the MEMS platform, the antenna can be fabricated with inexpensive optical lithography process. Second, the characteristics and performance of the tunable antenna are modeled and analyzed in detail. The series of numerical simulations based on the finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) method are conducted for the characterizations of the system in terms of the near field response to external light illuminations. The effects of the size, shape and gap of the antenna on the optical response and the field localizations are investigated.

2. Device description

The schematic of the tunable bowtie antenna is given in Fig. 1. It consists of two self-aligned identical triangular structures with nanoscale tips coated with noble metal (e.g., Au or Ag) thin film, forming the bowtie antenna. The triangular structures are integrated with two in-plane movable cantilevers, which are connected to and supported by the bent-beam electrothermal actuators [13]. The actuators are operated by an applied voltage or current source due to Joule heating, resulting in the in-plane movement of the apex of the bent-beams. Hence the gap between the two tips of the bowtie antenna can be modulated by the actuators.

Fig. 1 Schematic of the MEMS-based tunable optical bowtie antenna

3. Device design, modeling and performance evaluation

MEMS platform: The MEMS actuators are designed to tune the gap of the nanoscale tips of the bowtie antenna. The accurate control ability of the gap size and the precise repeatability of the positions of the tips are important parameters to determine the consistent performance of the antenna. To this end, the actuator should be operated in a range in which the resistance of the actuator has constant value, which means that the temperature coefficient of resistance (TCR) of the silicon is very close to zero within the operation voltage range. Therefore, the joule heating in the actuator should be minimized. In this case the actuator has to be operated at low temperature, hence low operation voltage is required and desirable.

Fig. 2 Disp. contour plot of the part of the antenna tip obtained using finite element analysis

Fig. 3 Calculated disp. of the tip of the nanoantenna vs. actuation voltage

The typical length of each bent-beam actuator is 100-500 μm , the width is 5 μm and bending angle 2 radians. The calculated displacement of the tip of the triangle under different actuation voltage is given in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 using finite element analysis (FEA). It shows that at 1 V and 3 V, the displacement is about 50 nm and 950 nm, respectively.

The scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image of one fabricated device is given in Fig. 4. The prototype device is fabricated using silicon on insulator (SOI) wafer. Typically the thickness and width of the cantilevers are 2-5 μm and 10 μm respectively, the length (L) of the cantilevers is 500 μm . In this prototype, the cantilevers are suspended above the handle wafer layer. Next step, the handle wafer layer underneath cantilevers will be etched away, facilitating the assembly of the MEMS optical antenna with commercial near field optical system for the testing. Measurements using SEM imaging also confirmed that the resolution of the displacement can be tens of nanometers, indicating high accurate control capability of the gap size of the bowtie antenna by the MEMS actuators. It also shows that the excellent repeatability can be achieved at low actuation voltage (<3V). Note that usually the speed of the thermal actuator is limited by the cooling cycle [13]. However for this case, since the displacement of the nanoscale tip is typically less than 1-2 μm or 1000-2000 nm. The speed can be readily in KHz range or even in MHz range, faster than enough for near field optical applications.

Fig. 4 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image of one prototype of fabricated antenna

Fig. 5 Measured displacement of the tip of the bowtie antenna using SEM imaging

Tunable optical bowtie antenna: Similar to conventional aperture NSOMs, the bowtie antenna systems can operate in an active mode or a passive mode. In a passive mode, the presence of near fields in a given system induces local surface plasmon (LSP) resonances as the bowtie antenna moving close to a near field area. Overall scattering patterns and local field intensities are altered and, thus, the presence of near fields can be detected. In an active mode, light from an external source illuminates bowtie antennas. LSP resonances and sharp metal tips induce strong local fields within the gap between the two metal tips. Nanoscale materials located close to the bowtie tip interact with the local fields giving unique output responses. In either case, LSP resonances are one of key components. LSP can best be described as collective oscillations of free electrons in metals as a result of resonance to external light. LSP resonances largely depend on a choice of metals and shapes and the size of metal structures. Most common features of LSPs are field localizations and enhancements. In this section, we characterize local field enhancements occurring in the bowtie antennas system we propose.

Fig. 6 Schematic illustration of the MEMS-based tunable bowtie antenna constructed in FDTD computational domain. Left: topview. Right: front-side view. The dimensions and tip angle (θ) are donated. The gap between the two tips of the triangular structures is g

Fig. 7 FDTD computed electric field intensities, $|E|^2$. Intensity distributions in 2-D plane cut through bowtie metal films for $h = 300$ nm, $\theta = 30^\circ$, and $g = 30$ nm

Consider bowtie systems depicted in Fig. 6 with incident light illuminated from bottom side and polarized in the direction parallel to the gap between the two tips of a bowtie antenna. The dimensions of the bowtie shape metal films are set as h , g , and θ . The thickness of the metal film is set to be 50 nm. The antenna is formed by depositing the Au film on the micromachined bowtie-shape substrate. The thickness of substrate is assumed as 400 nm. The end of tips is approximately treated as 20 nm flat nose. FDTD simulations are carried out with auxiliary differential equation (ADE) approaches [14]. Frequency dependent optical properties of Au are rigorously included by employing Drude pulse two pole Lorentz model [15]. An ADE technique is applied to incorporate the frequency dependent dielectric model with time dependant solutions of FDTD computations [16]. Grid resolutions are set to be 5 nm in all 3-D spatial grids. Computational domains span 900 grid cells in x and y and 260 cells in z . All 3-D domain boundaries are terminated with uniaxial perfectly matched layers. A Gaussian beam chosen as the incident light contains wideband optical signals. A field observation point is set at 10 nm away from left side bowtie tip-end in horizontal direction and center region of a metal film in vertical dimension. Field localization tends to produce most intense light at the end of each tip. Depending on a distance between two tips, intensity at the center of a gap will significantly be reduced as the distance increases even if actual fields at the tips are high. Intensities measured at the center between two tips will not represent an absolute field enhancement factor when different gap sizes are considered and compared. Hence, the observation point setup used here is expected to give better consistency regardless of gap sizes between the two tips. We note that local field intensities rapidly decrease as it goes away from sharp tip and the true intensities at the metal tip can be much higher. This singular like behavior imposes inaccuracy associated with local field measurements in FDTD if one tries to measure it right at the tip surface. These errors can be reduced by taking extremely fine grid resolutions or moving measurement points a few cells away from the surface [17]. In this study, the latter approach is chosen. One calculated electrical field distribution is given in Fig. 7.

First, we consider bowtie antennas with $g = 30$ nm and $\theta = 60$ degree. Four sizes of bowtie antennas are chosen, $h = 200$ nm, 300 nm, 400 nm, and infinitely extended, i.e., covering whole substrates. In Fig. 8 (a), local intensity, $|E|^2$, enhancements are plotted as a function of wavelengths. From this, one can find that spectral responses largely depend on the size of bowtie antennas, i.e., the spectral position of a major peak is red-shifted as the size of a bowtie-antenna is increased. Since we exclude any influence from gap dependency by fixing the gap size, this behavior can be seen as the general LSP characteristics in which LSP resonances strongly depends

on the size of local particles. The intensity enhancement also becomes higher as h increases. In a given spectral window, $h = 400$ nm case shows the highest enhancement among the bowtie sizes considered here and we expect that there will be higher enhancements with larger bowtie sizes when longer wavelengths are considered. The minor peaks (with lower intensity enhancement) are also observed near the visible wavelength regions. Compared to a major peak, this peak has considerably low near field enhancements. Next, angle dependence is investigated. We choose $g = 30$ nm and $h = 300$ nm as the fixed structure parameters. Three different angles are selected, $\theta = 30^\circ$, 60° , and 90° . As shown in Fig. 8 (b), the spectral peaks are narrower and blue-shifted as the angle becomes smaller. Field intensity is higher for the smaller angle. Local sharpness of the tip-end is kept the same as the 20 nm flat nose introduced for all cases such that narrowed bowtie tip angle does not change local sharpness of metal tips. Hence, this angle dependence can be interpreted as a result of altered LSP resonances. It is worth to note that similar bowtie systems reported in Ref. [12] relies on previous theoretical studies conducted on bowtie systems with different size and shape [18]. As the results shown here, optimum wavelengths for LSP resonances depend on a size and shape of bowtie antennas and it is not clear whether their wavelength choices were optimal at current stage.

Fig. 8 FDTD calculated intensity, $|E|^2$, spectrum for different size and shape of bowtie-antennas. (a) h dependent near field enhancement with fixed $g = 30$ nm and $\theta = 60^\circ$. (b) θ dependent near field enhancement with fixed $g = 30$ nm and $h = 300$ nm.

MEMS platform proposed in this work gives an additional flexibility to control the gap size, g , of the bowtie systems. Figure 9 shows normalized near field intensity spectrums for three different gap sizes, $g = 30$ nm, 60 nm, and 120 nm. In Fig. 9 (a), major peaks in wavelengths near 1500 nm are presented. Peak positions are moving to shorter wavelength as the gap size increases. Since, for some applications, visible to near-infrared spectrum regions are more interesting, we also normalized spectrum for minor peaks in these spectral windows and present in Fig. 8 (b). The gap dependent peak position tends to be blue-shifted as the gap size becomes larger. Although bowtie systems we are investigating use different configurations in terms of the bowtie size, substrate, and spectral window, it shares similar behavior with previously reported results [19] in which peaks are blue-shifted as the gap increases up to 60 nm. However, we also observe that peak positions are still blue-shifting with $g = 120$ nm in our case. With our best knowledge, this could be an outcome of thicker metal film, 50 nm, and 20 nm flat nose at the tip-end used in this study producing higher capacitance effect [19]. In Fig 9 (c) and (d), gap dependent spectral peak positions are presented. For major peaks, Fig 9 (c), resonant peak positions of four cases, two sizes and two angles, change monotonically as the gap size changes. The differences in major peak positions among different choices of h 's and θ 's with a given gap size are not much different when the given gap sizes are changed, e.g., a peak position differences of $(h = 300$ nm, $\theta = 30^\circ)$ and $(h = 400$ nm, $\theta = 60^\circ)$ cases are 470 nm and 460 nm for $g = 20$ nm and 120 nm, respectively.

However, the minor peaks, Fig. 9 (d), exhibit different features. First, resonant wavelength shifts due to the change of the gap size are less prominent for $\theta = 60^\circ$. Especially, for $h = 400$ nm case, it can be seen that $\theta = 30^\circ$ case has the highest peak position for $g < 60$ nm and becomes lower than $\theta = 60^\circ$ cases for $g > 60$ nm. Second, unlike the major peaks, the smallest resonant positions are with $h = 300$ nm and $\theta = 60^\circ$. Figure 9 (e) and (f) show that the intensity changes with different gap sizes. For both major and minor peaks, intensities rapidly drop down with larger gap sizes. The differences in intensities for a given g among two h 's and θ 's are larger for smaller gap sizes and this values are reduced as the gap size increases. For example, the intensity difference for major peaks is 2730 with $g = 20$ nm between the square mark data point, $(h = 400$ nm, $\theta = 30^\circ)$, and the triangle mark data point $(h = 300$ nm, $\theta = 60^\circ)$, but this value is reduced to 197 with $g = 120$ nm. Obviously, this also

indicates that the amount of intensity modulation by altering the gap size can be controlled or optimized by choosing proper bowtie size and shape.

Fig. 9 Gap dependence in spectral response of bowtie antennas. Top two panels, (a) and (b), represent near field spectrum for gap sizes, $g = 30$ nm, 60 nm, and 120 nm with fixed $h = 300$ nm and $\theta = 60^\circ$ in two different spectral windows. Middle two panels, (c) and (d), are peak positions as a function of a gap. Bottom two panels, (e) and (f), are intensity enhancement plotted, y-axis is in log scale. Panels (c) and (e) are for major peaks found in spectral window of panel (a). Panels (d) and (f) are for peaks in spectral window of panel (b). The marks $\bullet$, $\blacksquare$, $+$, and $\blacktriangle$ denote the following pair of structure parameters: ($h = 400$ nm, $\theta = 60^\circ$), ($h = 400$ nm, $\theta = 30^\circ$), ($h = 300$ nm, $\theta = 60^\circ$), and ($h = 300$ nm, $\theta = 30^\circ$), respectively.

4. Summary

This paper reports a MEMS-based tunable bowtie optical nanoantenna for the *first* time. The capability of the nanometer resolution and repeatability offered by the MEMS actuators paves the way for the tunable optical antennas. The MEMS-based tunable antenna offers many advantages in terms of cost-effective fabrication, dynamic optical intensity enhancement, dynamic wavelength shifting and performance optimization, etc.

The detailed optical modeling results show that the spectral responses are determined by the size and shape of the nanoantenna, which can span broadly from visible to infrared wavelength range. It also shows that the peak wavelength and the intensity of the spectral response vary with the gap size between the tips of the nanoantenna, thereby resulting in an ultra-bright wavelength-tunable nanoscale optical source.

A variety of applications can be anticipated for the tunable optical nanoantenna in nanoscience, nanotechnology, bioscience and biotechnology. More specifically, it could be used for nanoscale imaging and

spectroscopy such as nanoscale resolution chemical mapping of nanomaterials, ultrahigh density data storage, nanolithography, fluorescence and Raman signal enhancement for single molecule detection.

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